

Generation of Supernova Spectral Evolution Templates

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ABSTRACT

The advent of improved large sky surveys necessitates the development of photometric methods of transient classification, due to the resource limitations of spectroscopic analysis. This paper introduces a photometric approach to supernova identification, using a Python package named 'extrabol' (2). Extrabol transforms photometric data into bolometric light curves using Gaussian process regression and blackbody laws. This method does not rely on assumptions about the system's physical properties and aggregates data across energy bands to calculate bolometric flux. The bolometric flux allows us to study the temporal evolution of supernovae and infer their physical characteristics.

The focus of this paper is on the development of templates to guide 'extrabol' in predicting supernova evolution. By analyzing over 500 spectroscopically verified supernovae, focusing on types Ia and II, we established average light curve templates. These templates inform 'extrabol' about expected supernova evolution, allowing for more accurate predictions, particularly in data-sparse scenarios. Our templates were derived from the averages of bolometric luminosity and temperature, weighted by uncertainty, and formulated using blackbody laws.

Testing the templates involved simulating observational gaps and assessing 'extrabol's performance in filling these gaps. Results showed a significant improvement in prediction accuracy, as evidenced by a reduction in mean squared error. These templates allow us to model the spectral evolution of supernovae with greater accuracy, with the ultimate goal being to develop a predictive classification system for supernova types.

1. INTRODUCTION

Historically, supernovae have been classified spectroscopically, with astronomers typically looking for signatures of specific elements in the supernova's spectrum to identify it. However, spectroscopic analysis is quite resource intensive. It requires specific instrumentation, long observation times, and is difficult to do on dim sources.

This is of particular importance with the upcoming development of large survey telescopes. We expect these surveys to find thousands of events a night, which is far too many to verify spectroscopically. Our goal is to develop photometric methods to identify supernovae since photometry is much easier and quicker than spectroscopy, making it more suitable for large scale surveys. To do so we must be able to predict how an event will evolve, often with incomplete data, to highlight events that are of interest and are worthy of follow-up analysis. This will require accurate models of how supernova light curves evolve over time, described by the templates we produce.

2. METHODS

The estimation of bolometric flux in our study utilizes Gaussian Processes for interpolating transient light curves. A Gaussian Process assumes that any subset of points within our data adheres to a multivariate Gaussian distribution, and is characterized by a mean function and a covariance function. This covariance function establishes the relationship between each point in the light curve with every other point. The parameters in our covariance function are estimated through maximum likelihood estimation. After the light curves are interpolated, estimates for the radius and temperature of the body are fit using blackbody laws. The final bolometric flux is produced by integrating over all wavelengths at a specific time (3).

The blackbody radiation of the supernova is modeled using Planck's law, given by the equation:

$$B(\lambda, T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k_B T}} - 1} \quad (1)$$

where $B(\lambda, T)$ is the spectral flux density, λ is the wavelength, T is the absolute temperature, h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light in a vacuum, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

Figure 1: Light curves of transient 2020lbf demonstrating the multicolor photometry data from PS1 and ZTF surveys. Each color represents a different energy band. Each point is an observation, with the lines representing our Gaussian Process interpolated values. The shaded region corresponds to our uncertainty.

Figure 2: Black body evolution for transient 2020lbf.

Figure 3: Bolometric luminosity evolution for transient 2020lbf.

The primary advantage of Gaussian Process regression is in its non-parametric nature, which makes no assumptions about the system being modeled. This gives a Gaussian Process regression the flexibility to interpolate any time series, which is useful when dealing with the variety of transients observed. However, the lack of assumptions also allows for improvement. The prior on the mean function is set to zero by default, which we can improve upon. In particular, a prior set to zero struggles with temporal gaps in data, as the Gaussian Process' estimates will tend toward zero given

a lack of data. Our templates will be providing informed mean functions, based on observational data, to improve upon this.

The dataset used in this study is part of the official Zenodo data release corresponding to the Young Supernova Experiment Public Data Release 1 (1). This dataset includes multi-color Pan-STARRS1 (PS1)-griz and Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF)-gr photometry lightcurve files, formatted in the SNANA data structure. The dataset comprises 1975 transients, each associated with host galaxy data, redshifts, and spectroscopic or photometric classifications.

The central focus of our work is the generation of light curve templates to inform the mean function of the Gaussian Process, moving beyond the constant zero function. This is achieved by analyzing over 500 supernova events, which have been previously verified spectroscopically, focusing particularly on Type Ia and Type II supernovae. These supernovae are selected due to their distinct light curve characteristics: Type Ia supernovae exhibit remarkable similarity due to the Chandrasekhar limit mechanism in accreting white dwarfs, while Type II supernovae display characteristic light curves influenced by the ionization of their outer shells.

To create our templates, we first process these events using 'extrabot' to obtain estimates for the bolometric flux and physical properties over time. For each type, we calculate the average of bolometric luminosity, temperature, and radius over time, weighted by uncertainty, and smooth these values with a rolling average. Using the aggregated data, we create a template based on blackbody laws by calculating the spectral flux density at every wavelength that is consistent with our observed physical properties at each point in time. This template takes the form of a 2-dimensional array predicting the evolution of every wavelength over time.

Figure 4: Type Ia Supernovae Bolometric Luminosities

Figure 5: Type Ia Supernovae Temperatures

Figure 6: Each line represents the average spectra at different moments in time, corresponding to slicing our 2-dimensional template array.

Figure 7: Each line represents how the flux densities for different wavelengths evolve over time, corresponding to slicing our 2-dimensional template array in the other dimension.

We choose to focus on bolometric flux because it provides a better description of a supernova's temporal evolution as an aggregate of all energy bands. Furthermore, by using blackbody laws to estimate each wavelength's evolution

from bolometric flux, temperature, and radius, we ensure that our templates are grounded in physics. By using these templates as a prior for our mean function in 'extrabol', we ensure our regressions are more closely aligned with observed behavior and are compliant with blackbody laws.

3. RESULTS

To test the effectiveness of our templates, we simulated temporal gaps in our observations by removing 30-day intervals of data from our event records. We then used extrabol on the remaining data to predict the removed values.

Figure 8: Extended gaps in data are not uncommon, as seen here with this particular source. Our test is essentially mirroring this by artificially inducing such gaps. Note the dip caused by the lack of data when using the default prior mean of zero.

The results of our study demonstrate the efficacy of utilizing templates in the prediction of supernova light curves. We compared the observed values against those predicted by 'extrabol' both with and without the implementation of our templates.

Figure 9: Comparison of Type Ia supernova observed values versus predicted values without a template (left) and with the template (right).

Supernova Type	MSE (No Template)	MSE (With Template)
Type Ia	0.93	0.54
Type II	0.94	0.36

Table 1: Mean Squared Error (MSE) comparison for Type Ia and Type II supernovae predictions.

The mean squared error (MSE) was calculated for both Type Ia and Type II supernovae, with and without the use of templates, to quantify the improvement in prediction accuracy.

As shown in the figure and the table, the implementation of templates significantly improves the accuracy of the predictions. The models that use the templates have their points much closer to the diagonal on the scatterplot, and they also experience a significant decrease in MSE.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has focused on the production of templates to aid in the identification of supernovae by employing the 'extrabol' tool, which transforms photometric data into bolometric light curves using Gaussian Process regression. Our analysis covered the spectral evolution of over 500 transients, focusing on their light curves and temperature fluctuations over time, as reflected in the presented figures. The ability of the templates to compensate for observational gaps has been demonstrated, showcasing their utility in real-world astronomical analysis where continuous data collection is often unfeasible.

Despite the success of these initial templates in enhancing the prediction accuracy of supernova characteristics, we recognize that there is substantial potential for improvement. The parameters currently used in the generation of these templates can be further optimized to refine the accuracy of our predictions. Moreover, the complexity of the templates could be increased by incorporating additional parameters, which may capture the nuances of supernova behavior more effectively.

Moving forward, the incorporation of more sophisticated methods, potentially involving machine learning algorithms or more advanced statistical techniques, could provide a significant leap forward in our template refinement process. The ultimate goal of this project is to reach a point where we can predictively classify supernova types with high precision, leveraging the full potential of photometric data. This goal not only promises advancements in our understanding of stellar evolution but also has the potential to significantly impact the broader field of astrophysics by providing an alternative and more efficient method for supernova classification.

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